

Average PSD across bands and conditions for a sentence
"PC-GITA - laura"

Average PSD across bands and conditions for a sentence "PC-GITA - loslibros"

Average PSD across bands and conditions for a sentence "PC-GITA - luisa"

Average PSD across bands and conditions for a sentence
"PC-GITA - micasa" (*manuscript example*)

Average PSD across bands and conditions for a sentence "PC-GITA - omar"

Average PSD across bands and conditions for a sentence "PC-GITA - rosita"

